

phos and diazinon are unknown. Past experience with diazinon for BPH control also yielded different greenhouse

and field trial results. Diazinon has always given poor BPH control in the field. Whether or not monocrotophos is

an effective BPH control in the field needs further assessment. *h*

Orthoptera pests of transplanted rice in hills of Uttar Pradesh

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Grasshoppers, crickets, and a mole cricket have been found to cause heavy damage to transplanted rice in the hills of Uttar Pradesh. Damage is most severe in the nursery. Sometimes, the leaves of seedlings are completely eaten, leaving only the midrib and stalks. Before infesting a rice crop, nymphs and adults generally feed on grasses growing on rice field bunds or on sorghum and

Orthopteran species causing rice seedling damage in the Uttar Pradesh hills, India.

Family	Species	Intensity
Acrididae	<i>Acrida exaltata</i> (Walk.)	Moderate
	<i>Catantops pinguis innotabilis</i>	Low
	<i>Hieroglyphus banian</i> (F.)	High
	<i>Oxya fuscovittata</i> (Marschall)	High
Pyrgomorphidae	<i>Atractomorpha crenulata</i> (F.)	High
	<i>Chrotogonus</i> sp.	Moderate
Gryllidae	<i>Trigonidium cicindeloides</i> (Serville)	Moderate
	<i>Teleogryllus occipitalis</i> (Serville)	Low
Tettigoniidae	<i>Euconocephalus</i> sp.	Moderate
Gryllotalpidae	<i>Gryllotalpa</i> sp.	Low

millet.

Ten orthopteran pests have been identified from 4 years' observations and the intensity of damage determined (see

table).

Identification of species was confirmed by the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London. *h*

Soil and crop management

Upland rice varietal reactions to aluminum toxicity on an Oxisol in Central Brazil

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Brazil is the world's largest upland rice producer. About 70% of this production comes from the central region (22% of the country's area) which is a tropical savanna locally called *cerrado*. Aluminum toxicity causes serious yield reductions in this region. A CNPAF research program was initiated to identify rice cultivars tolerant of aluminum toxicity in the field.

Soil at the experimental site had pH 5.2, 0.52 ppm available phosphorus, 0.25 meq exchangeable Ca + Mg/100 g soil, 15 ppm available potassium, and 0.55 meq exchangeable aluminum/100 g soil.

Either no lime was applied to plots, or lime was applied at 3 t/ha. All plots were fertilized with 50 kg N/ha, 44 kg P/ha, 50 kg K/ha, and 5 kg Zn/ha.

Varietal evaluation at high and low levels of aluminum, Goiás, Brazil.

$$\text{Lime response} = \frac{\text{yield in limed plot} - \text{yield in unlimed plot}}{\text{Al saturation of limed soil} - \text{Al saturation of unlimed soil}}$$

Al saturation values were measured at flowering.

They were plowed and disked 50 days before sowing and lime was broadcast and mixed with a rototiller. Fertilizers

were broadcast before sowing and disked into the top 15 to 20 cm soil. Seeds of 142 varieties were planted in